

Statelessness as Rule and Citizenship as Exception: Analysing Rights and Risks of the Chakmas in Arunachal Pradesh

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Politically, the Chakma tribal community, a small indigenous group located from Chittagong Hill Tracts of Bangladesh were uprooted painfully due to the decolonising projects of partition as well as de-partition, and now with the changes of geographical location to India their political status remains in an ambiguous location between identity of conflicting refugee(hood) and contested citizenship. Politically, as a mere figure of human bodies they are reduced to a contentious issue in Arunachal Pradesh. This paper unpacks the underexplored settings of marginalities and vulnerabilities in-between such identities in shape. Simultaneously, it examines the downtrodden processes of emerging necessities and compulsions that led the Chakmas to resort to a legal battle in Court to locate themselves justly in this universe of population. At times, although they succeeded in getting reliefs from the Courts, however, as the author observes, the State's political willingness is against the Chakmas' interest and is also contrary to the Court's rulings. The author argues that the State is a powerhouse on the verge of dismantling Chakmas' internal core self and indulging in its ultimate collapse. Instead of balancing societies, in reverse, the issue is now stalemated, politicised, criminalised and left in an extraordinarily suspicious precarity.

Keywords: Rights and Risks of Chakmas, Stateless, Citizenship, Refugee, Legal Battle

Introduction

Putting efforts into tracing the Chakmas' cross-currents in an academic venture alone is impossible without intervention through contextually informed legal knowledge, including justice, indigeneity, refugee conventions/laws, political violence and citizenship within political theory. The proposed piece is compiled around those themes and flexibly restricted to an interdisciplinary lens in the surface of intersecting historical and ethnomethodological domains. The knowledge advancement records that the Chakma and Hajong (CHs henceforth) tribe¹ of Arunachal Pradesh (AP hereinafter) in the concerned political world located alone limited to as a subsidiary legal and humanitarian play agency. They are treated as a political currency, a human number, a

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lowest to powerless racial dossier every 'other' can poke, and therefore, seems no alternative to annihilate the settings making 'Chakma' a wretch, Stateless. Yet, their alternative to exist is by way of making each self a State² as a responsibility of existence and transforming the remaining agencies of 'being Chakma' into a collective 'State' in exile, informal and probably in popular imagination until they are lost wholly or the last Chakma sink into dust of the land (Singh, 2016). It seems their existence through mutual bonding is highly dependent on internal power of holding themselves united because there is high external pressure to break/shatter them, particularly the pressure from the state as well as non-state agencies. Their efforts of entering State's domain have been highly critical, especially when they are trapped in-between spaces of nation-state building, and much advanced ethnocentric consciousness of a state. The causality of such unprecedented upheavals, like otherisation, hatred, xenophobia, etc., lies already in the intersecting political history due to gaps in India's anti-colonisation processes and nation-state building (Ahmed, 1996; Nandy, 1996). It is, therefore, what the Chakma tribe is known today, including problems locating a permanent address in India in general and AP in particular, all induced by 1947 partition side effects and today's necropolitical schemes (see Guhathakurta & Van Schendel, 2013). There were two major incidents that led the CHs into the above situations: consistent political and religious persecution, structural and appalling violence; and the immediate life-threatening environmental catastrophe due to the construction of Kaptai Dam. For which D.K. Singh (2010) calls them as "developmental refugee" also. The political persecution was due to difference of political beliefs, race, ethnicity. The CHs were explicit about integration with India since pre-independence and thereafter (Chakma, 2013). Consequent to above reasons, thousands of Chakmas, basically Buddhist from Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHTs hereinafter) and Hajong, basically Hindu from Mymensingh district of Bangladesh, erstwhile East-Pakistan, took refuge to India in the mid-1964 to 1969 (Chakma, 1992; Amnesty International, 1986; Chakma, 2010; Singh, 2010). The Hajongs were influenced by the first reason, whereas the Chakmas were flooded with both. These reasons have qualified them into the category of refugee as per international law, although they were resettled and empowered effectively by India as a citizen. From 1960s, their 'life and struggle' to get a permanent home address and gazetted political identity remain unsettled (Talukdar, 1998).

Methodology

The paper is developed at the backdrop of enquiring agencies of citizenship from both procedural and substantial point of view. It is designed with mixed method exploring the ideas, institutions and process of citizenship followed by simultaneous exercises of enquiring knowledge from the field. From this interaction, the paper transacts with the notion of marginality, vulnerability, and resistance about how the idea of survival get negotiated by the Chakmas and Hajongs (CHs henceforth) when the common people, the elite groups and the State explicitly demand rejection to them. They became typically a "rejected" and "unwanted" groups who lost themselves in the political history (Weiner, 1993). Despite, series of judgement in favour of the CHs citizenship are on paper, how things reverse 'on the mind' that is failing to materialise a political consensus for final settlement. It intersects with the idea of making people into an

unfit and non-belonging. For instance, while interacting randomly with fifty student members of AAPSU, the author found that most of them hadn't seen or heard the CHs in real life. They imagine them to be non-mongoloid by race, having a beard like Muslims in Bangladesh, violent, destructive, a population bomb over lakhs, and unfamiliar with the indigeneity of a tribe—which is not the accurate reflection of the CHs. Further, the author was served with experiences and firsthand information throughout participant observation, interviews, informal discussions and questionnaire from 2017 to 2018 with the CHs as well as the local tribal populace, particularly the neighbours (the Singpho, Mismi, Naga, and the Khampthi) of the CHs. The community age groups across college's students, youths, the senior citizens, and mostly the political activists and leaders to which Brubaker (2004, p. 10) calls "ethnic entrepreneur" (cited in Vandenhelsken, 2018, p. 89).

Conceptual Map

India, including the whole of South Asia, lacks any standard provision/rule outlining refugee definition, reception, determination, and protection; in fact, there is no such category of 'refugee' in India's statutes (Saxena 2007, p. 246; Bhattacharjee, 2008; Veerabhadran, 1994, p. 235; ISIL, 2001, p. 118). No doubt, India despite having international commitment to protecting refugee, but there is an absence of clear refugee law/policy (Raj, 2020). Notwithstanding, the Indian judiciary has a very critical role in protecting the human rights of the refugees, including the CH refugees (Veerabhadran, 1994). In Northeast India's Arunachal Pradesh which has mostly been peaceful amongst other states, with the frictions of the CHs with the 'citizenship regimes' there have been a lot of new issues arisen and conflicting (Roy, 2022). The unfinished project of citizenship has already tantamounted creation of a collective sense of 'us' and 'them'. A fault line mostly caused by local resistance to disallow the CHs as 'full and equal membership of the given political community' (Marshall, 1950). They are deprived of 'rights and responsibilities' which is allocated to a citizen by the state (Macfoy, 2014). It is therefore, for the CHs groups entering to a civic community with the 'goal of citizenship' has been highly critical (Joyal, 2013).

While the paper is central to the problem of identity and citizenship, however, it touches several other contours of ideas and realities. The paper, thus, contextually presents the concepts and arguments thematically.

Chakma — a Case Figure

The competing realities interweb with a series of claims and risks which the CHs interfaced with the Supergovernment³ may be discussed in four phases according to timeline: (i) 1964 to 1972, (ii) 1973 to 1987, (iii) 1988 to 2015, and (iv) 2016 to date. Accordingly, the *first* was a transitional phase of rehabilitation and resettlements, rights before recognition, accommodation and cultural assimilation with neighbouring tribes, and symbiotic integrity, a phase of 'Indianization' at the receiving end. It was in Jacques Derrida's (2005) sense an "unconditional hospitality". Here, *Phase II* witnesses core building guided by mixed and unidentified feelings, inputs from the periphery to fill a vacuum for central leadership against State-wide problems. The precipitation of

the CH refugee issue, half due to insecurity, rumours and urgency for taking relevant action, and the rest half with condensation of mixed feelings led to the creation of solid 'other'. Thus, the CHs were perceived as 'other', and that became one of the major challenges in the State's politics against which the central leadership (the core) was formed as a pan-Arunachal students' body and as a most popular actor. To dismantle the 'other', strategies were shaped for a mass movement, such as the crystallisation of peripheral leaderships through means of political attention, like pressing calls for *band* (shutdown Arunachal), and putting pressing charter of demands on government for taking desired action, otherwise facing violent consequences. Such consequences tantamounted state-wide destruction of state's properties, which released popularity of All Arunachal Pradesh Students' Union (AAPSU) more than the State Government (Prasad, 2007). *Phase III* witnesses turbulence over decades leading to the creation of uncertainty of life, outraging fear, penetrating discrimination, provocative speeches and adamant action, economic blockages and shut down of essential commodity supplies including medical aids, school education, and kitchen items, burning of homes and direct attacks, 'quit Arunachal' ultimatum and shoot at sight orders, snatching all rights and facilities, including infringement of right to life and liberty (Prasad, 2007; NHRC Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors., 1996). Such actions have re-produced a perpetual battle at Court. Besides, the re-capitalisation of the 'other' translated the CHs into an applicable political package for nurturing populist agenda of politics. Very soon, the CHs issue has been exploited and used as a political currency in the State. This power dynamic has escalated political leadership through popular imagination for redemption. This includes creating a deep space of manufacturing consent, critical possession of the government and then unleashing a state of complete denial. These exercises have forcefully pushed the 'other', the CHs, outside the periphery of the State by the organised elements. Resultantly, within a binary worldview the contraction of power between the dominant and resistive forces entirety has shaken the balance and somehow, we see jeopardised situations of rights and risks witnessed by the State. Thus, this phase may be categorised as 'horrors in a deep space', and the CHs sidelined at the losing end. *Phase IV* corresponds to a shade of stalemate trap imprisoning the CHs in a prison of isolated political shield and conscience within the broader Indian politics. This development has processed the CHs into a significantly degraded human labour force handcuffed, exploited, inaccessible, illiterate, destitute, abandoned, prone to anti-social activities and 'human trafficking' within the shield and even excluded them from the free economic market (Ahmed, 2022; Boruah, 2023). It is a 'stalemated doom' whereby the act of finishing the 'being' of humans by the State through other criminal negligence, terror, persecution, atrocities, targeted human rights violations and detachment of self from the body, which has turned the State into a criminal agency in the process of making the CH durably stateless (SAHRDC, 1997).⁴ Instead, the State expects these "citizenship interns"⁵ to survive with 'hopeless hope' while arresting them under 24*7 surveillance and control (Chakma, 2024a). While the State seeks a bailout of the CHs problems, simultaneously appealing to the Centre to relocate the burden to other states without expressing its genuine intention to bear its share at first (The Assam Tribune, 2024, April 24).

Phase I: 1964 to 1972

The Government of India (GoI) sanctioned hundreds of lakhs of rupees to registered refugees and provide relief facilities, migration, rehabilitation, and final resettlement with life amenities (Ghosh, 2016). Under the patronage of GoI, ever since the CHs stepped foot into the Indian territory and until the final settlement took place in the specified locations, the concerned government has poured protection, care and security while ensuring the allocation of various economic packages and opportunities for overall upliftment and arrangements for self-subsistence (Singh, 2010). Until the 80s, the government, to empower CHs, provided government services, subsidised food grains and other related commodities available from fair-price shops and allotted five acres of land alongside administrative and agricultural assistance to each family (Gilani, 1992, December 01). Under a group leader, some fifty to one hundred families were specified to make homes and then settle down after clearance of deep penetrating jungles into a liveable and arable place. Since the tribes were well informed about *jhum* cultivation and wetland agriculture, they were equipped with similar agricultural tools, seeds, seedlings, livestock, and financial grants as provided by the public administration.⁶ The tribe was expected to survive against the wild animals, massive flood, and wholesome livelihood from the forest and land. In fact, until the 80s, when their population grew, and the houses were settled into villages, several of them lost lives due to brutal and wild animal attacks; thus, hunting and gathering has been one of the side-by practices along with developing agricultural occupation.

It has also been observed that the tribes around the CHs share positive vibes, and years of co-existence have led to the development of pretty good economic, socio-cultural and religious ties alongside an understanding of peaceful non-interference. There are multiple yearly instances of inter-tribe marriage, exchange of merits at Buddhist and cultural festivals, and more significant business deals. However, at nuanced political lines, there seemed to be unaccommodating sentiments linked with prospective fear of being a micro minority in this belt, including a tendency of internal complain about the local scratches to Itanagar while being a thirst for a durable solution, either making the CH settled permanently in Arunachal Pradesh with conditions or outside because there has been too much politics often disturbing the present in the name of future. There seems to be tolerance and mutual understanding for the CH; however, due to a path to Itanagar for education where the neighbouring tribal students have a trend to go, they have necessarily revitalised their trivial local concerns with the core students' group. Still, it is somewhere evaporated or condensed with more extraordinary State politics, seemingly outbursts in time of vacation, in December-January or May-June. It is a way force: a core in Itanagar that collects intel of adverse effects from the peripheral undergraduate students, and with that, they find a 'place of importance' in the group; on the other hand, with the same force, the core reflects the trust of creating pressure to the CH and the government at large.

There is a short-term concern for students' domain interests apart from amalgamating students' politics with State politics (Prasad, 2007). Therefore, the CH imbroglio remains a "political ladder" as an extended business of politics for most politicians and student leaders with no permanent solutions (Bath, 2023, p.321). Thus, the CH achieves more

concern for interest and value in their being, which, in a way, guides and sets a genuine intention of presence amid local resistance to volatility. The more uprooting insecurity about the vulnerability of living appears, the more widely the CHs explored its embeddedness in creating deeper roots (adaptability and consciousness) and branches (fraternity of a worrying community) (Chakma, 2018b; Kamduk, 2016).

Besides providing books, scholarships and schools, with the same resurrection, a good number of them were also inducted into services in various government departments like the Special Service Bureau, now known as Sashastra Seema Bal (SSB), Central Reserve Police Force (CRPF), Assam Rifles, Indo Tibetan Border Police (ITBP) in defence establishments; and other departments, like Civil Engineering, Food and Civil Supplies, Arunachal Pradesh Police (APP), Public Work Department, Medical, Public Health and Malaria, Education, Forest, Land Management, Agriculture, Post etc. At the same time, they were issued trade and gun licences alongside ration cards and government appointment of village Panchayat Headman, locally known as *Gaonburah*, under the Assam Frontier (Administration of Justice) Regulation Act 1945 (Prasad, 2006; Singh, 2010; Chakma, 2024b).

Phase II: 1973 to 1987

After getting Union Territory status in 1972, AAPSU stroked back to the CHs through the government, and later, the government had to cooperate with this organisation due to the verge of popularity as political currency. Unfortunately, in the wake of the unfolding political rise shaped into a mass movement led by AAPSU, most first-generation CHs born in India employed in these fields had lost their government services, including economic benefits and political rights (Saikia, 1994). The CHs plague multiplied day and night throughout AP's emergence as a full-fledged State on February 20, 1987, and beyond.⁷ However, a handful of them could continue their service through political connections or by not having Chakma or Hajong as a surname either.⁸ Institutions like Panchayat were retained and continued with traditional Chakma customary practices without the State's recognition. Besides central government appeasement attitudes and failure of human rights agencies to pursue the state government, at the backdrop of the Indira-Mujib agreement in 1972 according to which the Chakma/Hajongs arrived in India before March 25, 1971, would be considered for granting Indian citizenship (EPW, 1999), the CHs were left with a scary and doubtful presence; as Singh (2010) has rightly observed, "East Pakistan has long ceased to exist, and Bangladesh does not even acknowledge them as its own people, let alone getting them back to the CHT", therefore, they have neither will nor ability to return (p. 22).

On the other hand, getting the name of Arunachal Pradesh as a Union Territory in 1972 was unsatisfactory as the democratic powers were in the Centre's hands. There was a slow pace of development due to fewer democratic institutions and a lack of regional political parties and leaders, and most of the brilliant students were absorbed by government administration (Baruah, 2003a). Gradually, in the 80's, many students who used to study in Calcutta, Shillong and Guwahati were inspired with the power of students politics, i.e., All Assam Students' Union (AASU) in Assam raising issues of public concern, like illegal migrants/foreigners from Bangladesh (Prasad, 2007, p. 1374).

However, with the massive setback of rights and opportunities by the state government, they typically returned to their original acute destitute position once again. Neither did they have a State now nor a place to go elsewhere; the present and future were at stake —jeopardised and blocked, however, pushing in the past. Contemporarily, another sample of rights before recognition is that a tiny percentage of the CHs entertain voting rights “before they are legally recognised as citizens”, and the rest are neither foreigners nor citizens of India (Bath, 2023, p. 17). Neither a defining refugee nor a constitutional (full and equal) citizen, but somewhere in “between refugee and citizen” (ibid., p. 13).

The establishment of the CHs derives legitimacy from the Central Government, which unilaterally bears constitutional rights to confer citizenship and is also responsible for the resettlement and rehabilitation of the CHs in the current State where the problems lie (Chimni, 1994). It occurred before AP Statehood governed the people with a shield. The shield did not work due to the Central Government’s intervention in the case of the CHs. Until the Indigenous groups realise this gap and escalate with the State’s power, the CH’s establishment has become twenty-three years old. The balances were shaken once the processes were abrupt when instead of people (Indigenous groups) to people (the CHs) negotiation and Government (State) to Government (Centre) dialogue and discussion, the discourse of finding solutions underwent disproportionately due to the direct and violent confrontation of the Indigenous groups spearheaded by AAPSU supported by the State government, with the CHs groups. Resultantly, due to overwhelming dominations and intrusions with power and politics to the CHs domain, as soon as Statehood was achieved sooner, the government was pressurised to prove its accountability to the Indigenous Groups accordingly, for the CHs, the Indian Court of law was the only rightful place to seek shelter, peace and justice. Today, the CH presence of existing and the ability of hope are due only to the court as their legality of sixty years of history in India is protected and justified as Indian citizens.

Phase III: 1988 to 2015

The re-enforcement of systematic repression by the Supergovernment against the CHs community was condensed once the status of the Union Territory of Arunachal Pradesh turned into a full-fledged state (SAHRDC, 1997). At the backdrop of the Assam Accord in 1985, due to AASU’s successful movement, consciousness against refugee influx was asserted by the students’ group All NEFA Students’ Union back in 1967 (renamed AAPSU in 1972). It caught momentum against the Chakma-Hajong refugee issue seriously in the mid of 1980s when one of the activists was killed by police firing on February 3, 1986, AAPSU announced him as “first martyr” (Prasad, 2007, p. 1375). It escalated further, demanding justice for the so-called martyr. The pressure group adopted methods like the Arunachal Band (shut down), hunger strike, and a unique process, i.e., the Quit Certificate Movement (dropping college education and burning degree certificates for nations) in the late 1980s and throughout the 1990s, questioning and demanding solutions to several issues (ibid.). Amongst these, it has succeeded in many issues except the Chakma-Hajong issue.

Likely, against the Chakma-Hajong refugee issue, the State government was

pressurised “to initiate certain actions that are termed either as violation of human rights or denial of basic human needs” (Bath, 2023, p. 224). Those who did not comply with it were accused of being silent and supportive of so-called illegal CH refugees or against Arunachalee.⁹ The binary politics unleashed by AAPSU in the late ’80s and ’90s snatched away every single right, recognition, distribution of facilities, and enfranchisement from the Chakmas (ibid., p. 225-226).¹⁰ Adding to these, it intensified human rights violence, committing organised crimes and atrocities like “burning of houses, denial of access to local markets to sell agricultural produce and educational opportunities, etc.” (ibid., p.230).¹¹ Featuring the ‘Quit Arunachal Notice’ and slogan, like “Chakma-Hajong Go Back”, the AAPSU body warned the Indigenous people of the State not to provide land facilities and local employment thereof to all the non-indigenous people, like Chakma, Hajong, Nepali and Tibetans (ibid., p. 237; Saikia, 1994, p. 3311). In pursuance, it also joined bigger regional bodies, like the North-Eastern Students’ Organisation (NESO). The CHs were harassed and humiliated at marketplaces, within their localities and at the Assam-Arunachal boundary gate regarding ILP.

The Chakma/Hajongs were trapped once in a suicidal situation when AAPSU, supported by then Chief Minister Gegong Apang, issued a ‘direct action’ rally inside AP; and outside, the Chief Minister of Assam ordered ‘shoot-at-sight’ to any CHs to counter AP Government’s policy (Saikia, 1994, p. 3311). The ’90s was a nightmare decade when the Chakmas guarded their night to sleep at daylight. The home wasn’t safe because it was the central target to uproot everything, including sanctioning economic blockade through suspending public distribution systems, businesses, shops, and the supply of essential commodities, like health care and medicines, due to which several Chakmas had lost lives (People’s Rights Organisation, 1992, pp. 47-54; Saikia, 1994). Chief Minister Gegong Apang, in contrast to the appeal by human rights agencies, revealed that “cases of human rights violation against the Chakmas were to be taken up only in Bangladesh, and not in Arunachal”.¹²

Furthermore, Apang used financial tricks called “cash-dole-policy” to allure Chakmas by giving cash of 1,50,000 rupees against surrendering refugee papers and then “leave the State voluntarily and settle elsewhere”, as a result of which many families had inter-district migration to avoid constant force (Bath, 2023, pp. 235-236). The Chakma issue fed so many political changes inside the State even the members of the Indian National Congress quit the party and formed a separate political party, i.e., the Arunachal Congress led by Gegong Apang to oust the Chakmas; however, it became unpopular within a decade (ibid., pp. 240-241). The same applies to AAPSU when it is accused of articulating and using the Chakma issue solely to elevate political advancement closer to the political establishment with no relevant material solution to the issue; instead, the other untangled problems pertaining to the student community were rampant (Aboh & Bath, 2023a).

The ’80s and ’90s problems were a creation of Gegong Apang’s political vendetta with the Indian National Congress (INC) at the centre and the Arunachal Pradesh Congress Committee (APCC) at the local level, which led Apang to create his own political party (Arunachal Congress) through the exploitation of the volatile political situations and social turmoil under AAPSU spearheads. As a villain at the helm of the

Chakma issue, Apang backed AAPSU and ignited the Indigenous mind (Prasad, 2007). As a political opportunist, he expedited AAPSU to deal with his political opponents and later, student leaders were “silenced either through repressive measures or material inducements”, and many were imprisoned, and that’s how Apang’s policy of “confrontation to appeasement” led AAPSU decentered and unpopular like ever before (Bath, 2023, p. 320).

Bearing a complete State of denial, life-threatening risks, humiliation and atrocities at public places, unsafe homes, markets, schools and public routes, some of the CH student leaders and activists, while dropping everything behind, sneaked out into the Assam border at the peaks hours to go to New Delhi for help in 1994 when AAPSU’s ultimatum to drive out the CH as supported by the Gegong Apang’s government in the State followed by ‘Shoot at Sight’ order to the fleeing CH in Assam by then Hiteshwar Saikia’s government (Saikia, 1994; Prasad, 2007). Following a series of interventions from international, national, and non-governmental human rights agencies, like Amnesty International, the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), and the People’s Union for Civil Liberties (PUCL), the tension at the issue declined gradually. The CH issue became unpopular around the state and somehow became the “prisoners of politics” in the state’s overall political imbroglio, as lamented by human rights activist Suhas Chakma (Chakma, 2024c). It is a manufactured discontent (Chakma, 2024d).

To this effect, with the help of NGOs and other human rights agencies, the CH knocked on the door of the highest court of the land for justice. At least eight cases have been shared together in different periods, of which four critical cases are still pending in the courtroom. It is illustrated in the following figure:

Sl No	Case Reference	Parties	Court	Case About	Status	Higher Appeal
1	Khudiram Chakma Vs Union Territory of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors	Khudiram Chakma Vs Union Territory of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors	The Gauhati High Court	Petition against the respondent’s order to shift the petitioner from a settled donated land	Dismissed [not in favour of Chakmas]	Review Petition Dismissed. [not in favour of Chakmas]
2	WP(C) No. 720 of 1995. [decided on Jan 9, 1996)	NHRC Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh & Another.	The Supreme Court of India	State’s obligation to protect the life and liberty of foreigners/ refugees	Dismissed [Appellant’s claims upheld]	Review Petition Dismissed. [in favour of CH]
3	WP No. 886 of 2000. [decided on Sept 28, 2000]	PUCL Vs Election Commission of India	The Delhi High Court	Seeking direction to ECI to include CH in the electoral roll	Dismissed [Appellant’s claims upheld]	Not Challenged

Sl No	Case Reference	Parties	Court	Case About	Status	Higher Appeal
4	PIL No. 52 of 2010. [decided on March 19, 2013]	AAPSU Vs Election Commission of India	The Gauhati High Court	Chakmas' Right to Vote and Requirement of Inner Line Permit	Dismissed [Respondent claims upheld]	Challenged and Pending
5	WP (C) No. 510 of 2007. [decided on Sept 17, 2015]	CCRCAP and Ors. Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors.	The Supreme Court of India	Grant of Citizenship to CH Refugees	Dismissed [Appellant's claims upheld]	Pending at compliance level.
6	WA No. 28(AP) of 208, 04(AP) of 2009, 36(AP) of 2010, [decided on Feb 16, 2012]	Sonaram Chakma and Ors. Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh and Ors.	The Gauhati High Court	Forcibly evict the Petitioners from their settlement land	Disposed of. [allowed the appeal]	Not Challenged
7	W.P(C) No. 766 (A.P)/ 2017	Ms Mirina Chakma Vs Arunachal Pradesh Public Service Commission & Ors	The Gauhati High Court	Employment Rights based on by-birth citizenship.	Dismissed for non-prosecution by petitioner.	
8	PIL No. 20 (AP) of 2017 [decided on May 10, 2022]	Amal Kumar Chakma and 8 Ors. Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh and 5 Ors.	The Gauhati High Court	State to notify/declare the 46 CH villages in AP under Panchayati constituencies.	Dismissed [respondents' claims upheld]	Pending

Figure 1: showing the shared Cases along with their status as per the timeline

Each of these cases has thin and thick layers of argumentative differences that attack the nuanced idea of indigeneity, refugee, and citizenship regimes. It explores unprecedented references towards interacting laws interconnecting the past, present and future discourse as guided by natural justice and humanitarian outlooks. The intersections therefrom ultimately push the edges of constitutional democracy, transforming meaning and an idea of a modern state, and thus far, impacting political

understanding of India. As such is **SI No. 1**¹³, a group of 56 Chakma lawful refugee families who entered India via Tripura and shifted to Assam and then NEFA, now AP, who left the allotted areas and entered into a new jungle land area which was donated privately by local Singpho Raja of tribesmen in Miao sub-division, later it was recognised by the concerned District Commissioner through appointing village headman-ship to the Petitioner, including various other official exchanges. However, over time, when the Chakma group developed the area through consistent labour and cultivation into a likely settlement, the State challenged the private agreement/donation of the land to the non-citizens without informing the State and repeatedly ordered the group to shift to another place. Thus, Khudiram Chakma, the Gaon Bura (Village Headman) of Joypur village, filed a case against the State's order in the Gauhati High Court. The court examined basically three questions: whether they were citizens or foreigners; if foreigners, then does the State have the right to give direction to this group to shift to another place, and whether the impugned order was arbitrary, devoid of reason and violates the Constitutional provision.¹⁴ However, the court dismissed the appellant's claims based on the following points: that the entire group, including the petitioner, status of citizenship is void as per Section 6A of the Citizenship Act, 1955; Clause 2 of Bengal Eastern Frontier Regulation (BEFR), 1873 empowers the State government to have right to control over their movement, and similarly, has the power to prohibit foreigner of remaining in the State under Clause 9 of the Foreigners Order, 1945. Therefore, based on natural justice, as it seems in this case, the State's orders to shift them to earmarked places were allowed by the Court; however, the State would compensate the Chakmas for their money and labour invested therein and ensure the arrangement of alternative land, constructing houses and other essential facilities for shifting them.

Both parties ended up dissatisfied as one was losing cultivated land but gaining compensation, and the other felt the compensation without cause. Thus, both parties filed Special Leave Petitions (SLP) in the land's highest court.¹⁵ Same here, the Supreme Court of India examined that the concerned Chakmas were not citizens under Section 6A of the Citizenship Act, 1955 since they are of "Indian origin" (undivided India) and came before Jan 1, 1966, to Assam from East Pakistan (now Bangladesh, on March 31, 1964); however, they stayed in Ledo in Assam for some time only and then moved to NEFA¹⁶, therefore, cannot be considered 'ordinary resident'¹⁷ in Assam, which is a requirement to the Section 6A as per Assam Accord in 1985.¹⁸ Though a benefit seems due to the reason that AP is applied under the 'Immigrants (Expulsion from Assam) Act, 1950 (Act X of 1950) however, the subsequent 'North-Eastern Areas (Reorganisation) Act, 1971 bails the State of AP from the former Act. It upheld the Gauhati High Court decision that the State has the right to prohibit the acquisition of interest in land under Section 7 of BEFR, 1873, and Clause 9(2)(a) and 9(2)(b) of the Foreigners Order, 1948. Therefore, the State's order was rightful.

Whereas, on compensation, the Apex Court differed with the Gauhati High Court, as the latter directed for compensation based on humanity, and the former relied upon that since the land donation was illegal, settlement exercises and its location were violative of BEFR, 1873 and Foreigner Order, 1948, thus no case for awarding

compensation, however, directed to afford relief to petitioner sizable at Chief Minister discretion. With that, the court allowed the SLP of State of AP to dismiss Chakma's appeal.¹⁹

SI No. 2: At the vantage of the humanitarian crisis, the Chakmas approached human rights organisations across borders, including NHRC. However, upon finding it impossible to explore relief for the aggrieved CH from the State government, the NHRC moved the Supreme Court for relief. Therefore, it is NHRC applying Article 32 of the Constitution, through which the Supreme Court of India had to issue an 'interim order' on November 2, 1995, directing the State to maintain the rule of law and to ensure the safety and security of the CHs from non-State groups (AAPSU) immediately (NHRC Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors., 1996). Subsequently, in the final decision on 1996 January 9, the Court issued a writ of *mandamus* to the State Government and the Central Government directing to protect Article 21 of the Constitution, the life and liberty of the Chakmas, and except otherwise per law, no forceful eviction or drive be installed by State or non-State agencies to discomfort and deny domestic life. To ensure this, the State may take help from the centre's help for para-military or police force to repel organised groups like AAPSU (*ibid.*). Although the judgement was challenged for correction by the Arunachal Pradesh Indigenous Tribal Rights (Protection) Organisation (APITRO) and John Moyong separately, both were dismissed.²⁰

SI No. 3²¹: Based on the PIL intervention by a civil rights organisation, viz, People's Union for Civil Liberties (PUCL) to the ECI, the Delhi High Court directed ECI on September 28, 2000, to include eligible CH, born in India between 1964 and July 1, 1987, in the electoral rolls in AP. Accordingly, the ECI functioned; however, in 2003, a representation from CCRCHAP complained to the ECI that CH settled in AP despite having eligibility of being a citizen of India, they were not included in the electoral roll in four Chakma-inhabited legislative assembly constituencies. Accordingly, ECI ordered an inquiry and subsequently, based on the enquiry report in 2003, ordered a 'Special Summary Revision of Electoral Roll'. Resultantly, until 2019 general election, in four assembly constituencies, i.e., 14-Doimukh (ST) comprises 619 Chakma voters from a total of 21,961 voters, 46-Chowkham (ST) comprises 511 Chakma voters from a total of 14,058 voters, 49-Bordumsa-Diyun (Gen) has 3,020 Chakma-Hajong voters from among 18,188 voters, and 50-Miao (ST) has 569 Chakma voters from a total of 19,594 voters. Till 2019, the size of Chakma-Hajong voters (4,719) is 6.3 per cent of the total voters (73,801) in all four Chakma-resided assembly constituencies.²² The 4,719 Chakma-Hajong voters constitute 10% of the total CH population (47,055 as per Census 2011) till 2019. The ratio of the total number of eligible voters and the actual number of voters is disproportional and minuscule; the actual eligible population are denied voting rights (Asian Centre for Human Rights, 2008).

Due to the direct intervention of the Election Commission of India (ECI), in 2003, for the first time, a total of 1,497 Chakma voter applications were accepted from three assembly constituencies under Section 3(1) (a) of the Citizenship Act, 1955 (ECI, 2004). However, later, all the enlisted names from the electoral rolls were rejected by the concerned Electoral Registration Officers once the Arunachal Pradesh State Cabinet

passed a resolution on May 14, 2003, that Chakma-Hajongs are non-Arunachalee and require ILP under BEFR 1873. Upon this, the ECI reacted and further directed under Article 324 (1) of the Constitution, the concerned authorities, through the State Chief Electoral Officer, to revoke and revive the earlier decision to enlist 1,497 claims in the final electoral rolls, and since all 426 applications were rejected in 14-Doimukh (ST) assembly constituency and State's Cabinet resolution is violative and seemed a direct interruption to the power of ECI, the ECI thus has warned under 'compelling circumstances' that until the State withdraws the resolution above and create conducive conditions for free and fair preparation and revision of electoral rolls by ECI, "it shall not conduct any elections or carry out election-related work" in the four assembly constituencies (ECI, 2004). Despite a lot of objectionable boycott calls made by AAPSU and supported by the Indian National Congress and militant groups in the State, on March 3, 2004, before the Parliamentary election, ECI ordered to publish 2003 electoral roll with names of 1,497 Chakma-Hajong under Articles 325 and 326 of the Constitution of India and Section 19 of the Representation of the People Act, 1950 became voters long before their (grand)parents were conferred citizenship by the Supreme Court of India in 2015 (ibid.). The 2004 Lok Sabha election was held successfully amid AAPSU's protest, 'boycott call', threatful consequences to any person or political party filing nomination against the backdrop of the boycott election, slogans (like no solution, no election, no representation), a boycott to central government establishment, including the Hindi language, those political parties go against AAPSU referred as Anti-Arunachalee, etc. (Bath, 2023).

Yet with all odds, after 40 years of arrival, some CH could exercise citizen's rights for the first time in 2004; neither ECI stopped issuing, from time to time, guidelines for the revision of the Electoral Rolls substantially for inclusion of the CH, nor the State stopped taking advantage of the loopholes. For example, in response to the difficulties and challenges of not getting enough names accepted in the electoral roll, the ECI issued additional and specified guidelines in 2005 and 2007. In fact, once at a time, birth certificates were not accepted despite being admitted in the prescribed guidelines because, allegedly, those issuances were not informed by the Births and Death Act 1969 (Bath, 2023, p. 202). As the rejected applicants describe, the gaps are that the election registration officials are local/Arunachalee who, unlike ECI, are unwilling to make CHs eligible.²³ It is a vacuum where discretion applies utmost in the officials' minds before advancing any law enforcement gap. On one side is the State government, and on the other are the law and the Constitution. Both contrast whether to deal with associating the self-identity of *Arunachalee* serving Arunachal State government (which does not want the CHs); the other side being constitutional and lawful by abidance to an oath. Therefore, an apparent mutual trust is also an issue between the Arunachalee and the CHs. Therefore, tracing loopholes in the rules at best depends on the minds and moods of the officials.

Sl. No. 4²⁴: Against this flow, AAPSU filed a PIL case against the ECI in the Gauhati High Court, based on its 2005 and 2007 particular guidelines for bypassing not only BEFR 1873 in AP but also unreasonably discriminating against the people by favouring the Chakma-Hajongs who lack 'inner line permit' (ILP) as well, therefore, against the law (*AAPSU Vs ECI, 2010*); the ECI argued that it is as per law as well as

“in compliance with the order of the Delhi High Court” on September 28, 2000, and as per Article 324 of the Constitution, thus, no arbitrary or discrimination against parties (refer, *PUCL Vs ECI, 2000*). Out of this judgment, two things were cleared since the GoI took the CHs: fulfilling all local dues and concerns to resettle them with lands, rights and facilities in AP, it also means conferring them Indian citizenship, therefore, violation of ILP provision of BEFR, 1873 and undermining of “Section 13 of Registration of Birth and Deaths Act, 1969 does not hold water”; thus, the CHs do not require ILP, otherwise, such requirement would negate and defeat the settlement policy-plan or ‘definite rehabilitation schemes’ took by the Government of India. Secondly, ECI’s guidelines conform with GoI’s policy decision to settle the CHs and to grant citizenship. Thus, the right to franchise to a CH as a bonafide citizen of this country is also in the protected interest in conformity with those policies. Thereby, the court dismissed the PIL of AAPSU.

However, at a later stage, a ‘Special Leave Petition’ (SLP) was admitted by the same court filed by AAPSU against the judgement and order passed on 19th March 2013 by a Divisional Bench of Gauhati High Court (PIL No. 52 of 2010) ordering the ECI for inclusion of CH names in the electoral roll of the State.²⁵ The same is now pending at the Hon’ble Supreme Court.²⁶

Sl. No. 5:²⁷ Non-deprivation from citizenship rights to the CHs under Section 5(1)(a) of the Citizenship Act 1955 was seen in the light of the 1996 (SL. No. 2) judgement. Therefore, in pursuance, the petitioner, the Committee for Citizenship Rights of the Chakmas of Arunachal Pradesh (CCRCAP), sought direction from the Apex Court under Article 32 to recognise rights and take substantial action by the State through the conferment of citizenship to the original refugee migrants entered India lawfully and rehabilitated by GoI.²⁸ Citizenship has been the most precious right to have several other subsequent rights. While allowing the petition, the Court observed that subject to the procedure established by law, the CHs have the right to be granted citizenship and do not require ILP since they are settled inside the State’s territory. Further, seeing the GoI’s policy plan for rehabilitation, the verdict from the Delhi High Court, the Gauhati High Court, and the guidelines issued by ECI in line with protecting citizenship claims of the CHs, the concerned Court was satisfied, and, accordingly, directed GoI and the State of AP to “finalise the conferment of citizenship rights on eligible Chakmas and Hajongs and also to ensure compliance with directions in the judicial decisions referred to in the earlier part of this order for protection of their life and liberty and against their discrimination in any manner. The exercise may be completed at the earliest preferably within three months from today” (Para 21).

The 2015 judgement was on a landmark case; however, its directive to confer citizenship to “eligible Chakmas and Hajongs” demands direct supervision to scrutinise and validate who is eligible as unlike America, India’s legal prism indicates everything as per the procedure established by law, under which a refugee or any person(s) to be Indian citizen(s) has to apply for citizenship under Section 5 of Citizenship Act 1955 undergoing through examination of ‘genuine’ intention to reside in India permanently, taking an oath of allegiance, and showing befitting character. Although the Central Government has the sole authority to grant citizenship, the underlined procedure

specifies the requirement of State government's positive recommendation for it in the applications, which are procedurally scrutinised, verified and then approved by the concern State government administration before it went for final approval to the Central Government (Committee for C.R. Of C.A.P. & Ors Vs. State of Arunachal Pradesh, 2016; Jayal, 2013, p. 78). This democratic procedure sensibly and discretionarily gives the State a veto power; therefore, for the CH, it is not yet parallel or level-playing since prima facie, the State expresses unwillingness, and processing any citizenship application must pass through the State's litmus test and veto power. Therefore, given the circumstances of power friction, Bath has rightly observed, "...the attitude of the Government of AP indicates that the applications might be forwarded to the Central Authority with negative recommendations" (Bath, 2023, p. 185).

Already, from 14,888 original refugees, an aggregate of 4,637 citizenship applications²⁹ was submitted, of which 539 are missing from records (both Centre and State Governments), 271 were not sent back by the Home Ministry as the State argues (although MHA claims to have sent back all to the State) (Chakma, 2018a). All in all, 3,827 applicants were held for hearings subject to differences (ibid.). Following the differences in the proceedings, the Supreme Court-appointed Arunachal Pradesh State Legal Services Authority (APSLSA). It was observed that there have been severe anomalies in the applications for following reasons: (i) a prolonged due over papers examination, (ii) lack of constant reasons between federal government to care and communicate on each paper leading to blame and counter-claims and ultimately inability to retrieve it, (iii) quarter-size (precisely 919 applicants) of the number of total applicants have already demised waiting for a result, and only 1798 had attended the hearing, (iv) several signed in Clause (a) of the Citizenship Act 1955 expressing willingness to stay Indian permanently but missed the second schedule of the Act for an oath of allegiance, (v) some applications were rejected because over the years they came across civil cases pending in court, (vi) most of the applicants did not attend the hearing for reasons they didn't know about it, had no logistic sources to attend it, or undergone inter-district migration to other CH residential areas (precisely 915 applicants), (vii) some (precisely 178) were found duplicate and some (precisely 10) were triplicate. (viii) Before a benefit of the doubt is given to the missing and absent applicants for hearing, as expressed by APLSA, MHA's eagerness and political will are prerequisites.³⁰ Thus, it is still pending due to the following reasons: either the petitioner was not following it seriously for early disposal; either due to a political understanding or controversies between the Centre and the State government; due to lack of additional and substantiating documents among parties concerned to file a new affidavit; and either due to stronghold of the State through Kiren Rijiju, a powerful cabinet minister from AP in the Union Government. It's a time- and life-consuming exercise; the more time, the more complications there are.

The admixture composition of the CH issue with the legal-political dynamic stands today in a location where both the entities' limits intersect; one's end encounters the other's beginning. The grammar of exploring tensions and styles of countering paradoxical loopholes insight that given the limitation, the Courtroom cannot be a durable solution in this case as abidance to the Court's order seems to be externally a

forceful obligation/obedience or somewhat offensive for the State, not acknowledge of a transformative acceptance from inside the core's willingness. That's how the solution is reliable, more political than legal, seeing at least the widespread full-fledged state power rather than constitutionally institutionalised slow and procedural court. The gaps trouble the future concurrency of the rest of the non-applicants CHs or the psychosis of non-approved applicants regarding clearing the status as the term "eligible" in the Supreme Court directive overpowers the host State in the procedural set-up, especially when the government is in a reverse mode, reluctant, defeated at receiving end and fortunate enough to administer procedures independently; the questions are whether approval of atleast a single application would necessarily go one to one or en masse to all as a group or vice-versa since it seems the eligibility verification has been undergoing for merely 4,637 citizenship applications, not open to all original refugee/migrants with a fresh call for applications; whether recognition with approval by MHA would go vertically with individual citizenship inheritance or horizontally en masse to all as a group so far as a meaning of an ethnic group is drawn from the case; how would the Supreme Court jurisprudence deal with the CH whose eligibility testaments are illegible or lost in time and space (mostly during State backed AAPSU's targeted genocidal attacks and blockades before the administration).

Thus, with the term 'eligible,' the Apex Court has associated itself with the CH, and it might have to be medicine in the time of disease, at worst and bitter truth, until the government's political will provides enough scope or unless the CH surrenders. It is obvious now that inter-tribal space is taking shape, and it has different and complex political realities alongside the changing orientation of interacting social entities, i.e., often conflictual. The trajectory part of this sixty-year-old inter-penetrating movement for turning one's identity and status from a refugee to a full-fledged citizen is that there are less than 5000 of 14,888 originally resettled CH refugees are surviving, for most who are too old and close to dying soon, especially who lost themselves before the time/history "citizenship has almost become meaningless in the twilight of life" (Chakma, 2015, November 26). This dynamic also indicates how taking citizenship to a State is bestowed at the 'will' of the interacting governments (Roy, 2010). It also injects us with legal insights into how the futures of upcoming generations and until now are dependent on political determination of the status of the original (ancestor) migrants.

SL. No. 6: Undoubtedly, due to the absence of a concrete formula dealing with refugees, the CH enjoyed the benefit of the doubt; however, the absence is unfilled also due to the enlargement of political executive power, selecting exigencies based on discretion impacting kindly to both the policy and politics, as it is seen in the case of the State of AP, similar in taking privilege advantage of the legal-loopholes within its room at the helm of complying with the 2015 judicial direction. It is also due to the same kind of gap in the aforesaid case that the Gauhati High Court accepted the petitioner, Sonaram Chakma's prayers without giving specific direction to the State of AP. The petitioner appealed to the Court against particular orders by the State to forcibly oust them from their shifted settlement areas, namely Madhukanallah and Sukhranallah, substantially a part of the allotted initially Khagam resettlement area. Based on specific claims, it was a bit similar to the Khudiram Chakma case; however,

it was different because most of the arguments placed were tallied with those already by NHRC, shaping the Supreme Court judgement of 1996. Therefore, the Gauhati High Court confirmed the 1996 direction in the record for ensuring life and liberty and protecting the property of the CH with no forcible eviction or drive by organised groups. Also, it confirmed that the said settlement area had been inhabited by the CHs much before the Arunachal government adopted Assam Forest Regulation 1891, and due to the absence of a rule of eviction in existence until the CHs resettled already, and therefore, much later in May 2010, when the State of AP had published Arunachal Pradesh Forests (Ejectment of Unauthorised Persons) Rules, 2010, is not logical to drive the CHs out from the settlement while taking recourse from the Regulations 72(c) of Assam Forest Regulation 1891. Thus, the petitioner was considered a non-encroacher of Forest Regulations.³¹

Phase IV: 2016 to date

Sl. Nos. 7 and 8: There are currently at least two cases, i.e., AAPSU Vs Election Commission of India (2013) and Amal Kumar Chakma and 8 Ors Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh and 5 Ors (2022), that are prominently pending inside the Courtroom concerning the eligibility of the CHs, who claim to have by birth citizenship and therefore, have entitlement of right to electoral franchise, and the right to have Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) respectively, for local self-governance. Based on ambiguous citizens' rights entitlement, at least two challenges emerged recently. Firstly, in 2016 four Indian-born Chakma candidates, including Mirina Chakma, faced racial discrimination and were denied examination to be recruited into public services by the State (Arunachal Pradesh Public Service Commission) because of the fact that “they belong to the Chakma refugee community who has not been granted Indian citizenship by the Government of India as the AAPSU have (sic) filed a Special Leave Petition before the Hon’ble Supreme Court of India” (APPSC, 2017, October 26).³² Against this, as a regular judicial help, a case before Gauhati High Court, Assam, was filed seeking the court’s intervention.³³

Secondly, Based on the exercise of voting rights, the CHs could participate only in the parliamentary and assembly elections, not at the local Panchayati level since there are no recognised Panchayati Raj Institutions in their village, so far as the villages have recognised names but dealt by the State as more giant refugee camps, not enlisted by the State Election Commission, as per Article 243 of the Constitution. Therefore, specific claims were made by the Indian-born CHs regarding the right to participate in the Panchayat election in their respective villages. However, the Guahati High Court dismissed the plea for reasons that no competent authority including the highest court of the land have already declared them as citizens; that, absence of any competent representative as respondent from reportedly affected tribal/indigenous group due to any possible judgement hereinafter, as the concerned Deputy Commissioner cannot be considered the representative of the people where the CH are settled; that, the matter of claiming citizenship by the descendent of non-citizen or refugee under Section 3(1)(a) and 3(1)(b) of the Citizenship Act is pending before the the Supreme Court of India as from 4,637 citizenship applications, 2029 applications were found duplicate/triplicate or absent or already expired, and 3837 applications were recommended by

the State as “ineligible”, thus, in such circumstances, the prospective decision by the Apex Court may touch some new interpretation touching about the descendents of the refugee parents who born in India; that, a Special leave Petition is lodged in the Supreme Court of India by AAPSU Vs. Election Commission of India and Ors. (SLP (Civil) CC No. 21861/2015), and State of Arunachal Pradesh Vs. Election Commission of India and Ors. (SLP (Civil) No. 17762/2016), which is pending considering the Chakma and Hajong as citizens to be electors.³⁴ After dismissal from the Gauhati High Court, the case is now pending at the Supreme Court of India.

From a vantage point, the author sees that the radiation from the legal battles has undoubtedly released negative energy more psychologically, causing a rift in relationship and understanding, more tensions and rivalry, and misunderstanding between and among the CHs and Supergovernment to achieve a complex sense of relief in defeating each other’s ‘other’ in making one’s space better. That now is more of an attribute of narrowed, non-compromising pursuance of competitive political interest, victory, and strategical preparation. That suggests that CHs should have more legal-political awareness and that AAPSU should rebuild itself by focusing on the political currency of itself. The problem is that the final resort to the Court preceded the dialogue and discourse between the parties. Until then, the CH has diluted to a mere court figure; both (Supergovernment and the CH) started at two opposition ends based on claims, perspectives, causality, and frame while also seeking two contradictory solutions. Eventually, the sooner the tensions escalated enough, the more fragile the arrangements for sit-in-dialogue became and mostly failed.

Rights and Risks Analysis

Analysis 1: ‘Original’ Refugee Migrants³⁵

These cases determine whether the CHs (except otherwise the pending compliance of the Apex Court verdict of 2015 to the original Refugee migrants) born in India in generations are to be considered citizens or not; if yes, then as a rights-bearing citizen access denial to all rights and privileges by the State is justifiable or not. As a level-playing independent agency, although the ECI, through its guidelines, cleared the status of the CHs back in 2004, in addition to the Delhi High Court, Gauhati High Court and the Supreme Court of India.³⁶ It seems, for the CHs and the State, the battle in the courtroom for ‘heart and home’ is over, and now the rest on the political execution mainly on the field, politics and parliament, even though there is already a green signal from the parliament’s 105th committee report’s recommendation on August 14, 1997, to grant citizenship rights along with ST recognition to all the CHs who arrived before March 25, 1971, the GoI has not acted on upon it.³⁷

Although the Government of India, particularly the Union Home Ministry, has the unilateral right to action on this subject, it is unable to take it either considering the State’s local, emotional and political competing criticalities/interests and simultaneously considering the other strategic sensitivities, like it shares an international border with giant China along with Bhutan and Myanmar (Baruah, 2003a); as to avoid creating another Mizo or Naga movement, as Indigenous groups including AAPSU and political parties threat to develop extremist, secessionist based protesting culture in mind; and

it is reluctant to damage immediately the faithful relationship earned during a lengthy historical process of Indianization of this zone (ibid.). Bath laments the central government's casual attitude "all is well" (Bath, 2023, p. 249).

*Analysis 2: Descendants*³⁸

Until now it is clear that the CHs, particularly the descendants, unlike the Rohingya refugees, are considered as *de jure* citizens, if not *de facto*. G. Talukdar, age 67, rethinks "whether the CHs have been moving in the same direction as the Supergovernment left the trajectory since the CHs were located, benefited and brought up at par citizens until the AP Statehood and from there, the State translated identity and somewhere grammared at State's narratives because of which instead of 'restoration of rights', the CH bodies framed to claim citizenship rights; had it has been slightly altered then today's calculation of outcomes would have a different paradigm".³⁹ This framework of thinking no doubt leads to a conspiracy theory for hijacking the mind of an entire community. Still, while skipping this theoretical inquiry, this piece critically delineates that a current body of CHs, the 'Chakma Rights and Development Organisation' (CRDO), was established to reclaim the similar space they had during the early two decades for the new generations born in India.⁴⁰

The concerned cases are paused between the arguments that even if the petitioners (descendants) claim to be a citizen by birth, having a birth certificate, voter card, Aadhar Card and other government documents, and therefore entitled to any rights, privilege and service so far, a citizen can have. The arguments by the respondent, i.e., the State or its agencies, push the CHs back to the original battle of citizenship of their parents and grandparents (the original migrants). Hence, even if one has voter card, the "authenticity of voter card is yet to be ascertained" by the government in line with confirming citizenship.⁴¹ The government is reluctant, thus follows citizenship process of 'descent' rather than by 'birth' which is to twist the complexities. Even if a CH is born in AP, they have to re-connect their establishment of inheritance of legitimacy, knowing that their (grand)parents are not bonafide Indian citizens as of now (ibid.). Apart from that, there is already an SLP pending in the Apex Court deciding the ground of legitimacy of giving citizens' elector power to the CH refugee by ECI even before the Apex Court judgement arrived in September 2015. It basically challenged the exercise of citizens' rights of voting before procedural approval of conferring citizenship as powered⁴². Since it is yet pending in the Court, any benefit entitlement to the CH under the State is also indefinitely empty, unless the proceedings of the above cases in Court are effectively positive. The CH was once again trapped in court cases urging priority of adjudicating themselves clear from refugee identity and then transforming 'deemed' citizenship and citizenship 'interns' to finally approved citizenship and, at the receiving end (host State).

It sounds a perennial issue in the making, and this trend will continue once developed. This loophole even unpacked a chance for the Supergovernment to start afresh denial of the State's direct benefit, like the deletion of refugees' "names from the electoral rolls," condemning the judgement "away from a logical solution".⁴³ Further, the Arunachal Pradesh Legislative Assembly has passed a resolution against the CH recently not to grant citizenship. Until recently (in 2022, to be exact), very few rights,

like issuing a Residential Proof Certificate (RPC) for job and educational purposes only, were withdrawn by the government affected by this trend; instead, a 'Temporary Settlement Certificate' (TSC) is issued by the state categorising them en masse refugee and their residence as camp (p. 261).⁴⁴ Due to consistent State denial, the population has to meet massive hunger and starvation during the CoViD-19 pandemic, which human rights agencies have lamented as a purposeful and systematic act of denying the right to food — “an act of inhumanity and cruelty” (Bath, 2023, p. 227). Thus, the CHs' present still depends on the past; the historical burden is a trap that stimulates the CHs' history in today's 'political'.

The case problematises the practical limitations of a judicial system as one of the most crucial pillars of the government, sharing some overlapping loopholes with its companion pillars, the legislature and executive, within the shades of State and constitutionalism. This reminds us relatively of the position of the Arunachal Pradesh government or the State apparatus of AAPSU, with the symbol of absolute monarchy, King Louis XIV of France saying the phrase, “*L'État, c'est moi*”, meaning, I am the State, literally, “the State, it is me”, which re-adjusts our mind rethinking whether the nuanced ideas of exclusivity and the divine right of indigeneity conflicting with or probably overriding the processes and institution of constitutional citizenship of a State inside a shield (Rowen, 1961).

Notwithstanding the imbroglio in the State's design, the CHs in AP may also be considered as “denizens”, having been seen as foreigners although residing in India for decades and possessing certain citizens' rights without being recognised as actually non-full-fledged citizens (Hammar, 1990; Lucka, 2019). The balancing ties amid court cases and space of politics in the State intersect myriad push and pull-based forceful tensions, which explore parameters of remedial exigencies. Given the negotiating resistance, the underlying marginalities rampant to the CHs in this exercise have caused a future threat of human poverty in which the concerned segmented with utter vulnerabilities socially, economically, and politically (Ghosal, 2018). With no exception, an intrusion into the CH cultural 'self' remained trivial at the edges of ethnic boundaries. The embedded confusion around cleavages of complex realities has challenged the legal intellectual traditions to explore the dimensions of 'multi-layered citizenship' with the rise of CH case in India (Baruah, 2003b).

Conclusion

The location wherein the CHs today is fixed, highly territorialised, and stalemated. Based on the problems there seems too many questions over the law and order, and the implications of the citizenship laws at the Central level as well as at the local level. There is a gap between legislation and execution, imposition and acceptance, and Central norms of equality and State's norms of “differential citizenship” (Young, 1989, p. 258). In these gaps, the CHs are in a political conundrum and impasse losing every breath for a recognition within the constitutional framework. In a pathetic situation, the CHs are earning everyday of peace at the expense of life and time. Both are irreversible. With time, the way legal complexities are increasing for them, the case of CHs is getting foregrounded to humanitarian crisis expecting a little hope for citizens' rights, a sizable land, and an opened peace. The junction between the humanity and

political law seems naturalising a question of how a democratic government, as a custodian of the State power, is so overwhelmed and so powerful to dishonour and harass a population's existence continuously while, at a seminal point, they were rehabilitated permanently by the Government of India with all due respects, accords, facilities and rights, and still so stubborn to de-establish them that recommendations from Human Rights agencies, several Members of Parliament (from both Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha), and local Indigenous tribesmen to resolve and recognise the CH as citizens are outrightly rejected. Despite series of judgement in favour of conferring citizenship to the CHs, there have been evidently attempts to compromise the judgements, particularly with indefinite delay in execution. In fact, to make citizenship as an exception and statelessness as rule from the State's side, the government concerned sought loopholes in between the existing and emerging Constitutional provisions and the Courts' judgements. For example, under the leadership of Kiren Rijju, a former Union Law Minister from AP, the State of AP was exempted from implementation from a recent statutory law, i.e., the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) 2019, which puts a cut-off date of December 31, 2014, for acceptance of foreigners belonging to religions, like Hindu, Sikh, Buddhist, Jain, Parsi and Christian minorities, except for Muslims (Islam), from Bangladesh, Pakistan and Afghanistan countries (Mander, 2021, P. 2). On target, the Chakma Buddhists and Hindu Hajongs were policy-deprived and discriminated systematically against for the last sixty years. Astonishingly, similar issues of all refugees/foreigners of CH's contemporary in old and new India have been solved, except them. In an exception category, now, the CHs consider themselves Indian, and the preclusion from CAA 2019 does not affect them enough because they were resettled already by GoI and already have explored routes of citizenship from Section 5(a) and Section 3(1)(a) of the Citizenship Act 1955.⁴⁵ It not only "contradicts the secular principles" but also presents a "selectively exclusive citizenship model" in the Constitution.⁴⁶ The biased policies by the State, thus, unpack *refugefication* policies to the already Indianised ones.

Even if the CH gets citizenship rights with ST status tomorrow, that's 'too little' to count on in history, and yet it's too exhausting to always be in the rival. And even if the government could possibly materialise its course, expelling or eradicating the CH, the question before the Supergovernment is that someone, a new 'other', might be replacing the CH. Even in this stalemate situation, the problem is heading towards creating terms and conditions for the CH to let them stay or leave, either with "limited citizenship" or 'relocation' to another State(s) (Chakma, 2017, September 21; The Wire Staff, 2024, April 24). Such attempts were made in 2015 and 1966 and have failed, respectively. Thus, everyone, including the State, is at a loss in this seemingly challenging political game: spending lives buying time only around court cases, making no one more humane and no happier alone. The question is to rethink whether to choose peace of mind through multicultural co-existence through political solutions or suffering throughout Court cases.

Since strategies like lobbying and dialogue with the political leader at multiple levels failed to shape a concrete political will at the outcomes, today's stalemate situation has arrived due to legal battles yet slightly better than the turbulences faced during Phase III. This development indicates that legal struggle is inevitably necessary.

Simultaneously, the interface of counter-filing between parties would unleash an endemic cycle unreachable to a durable solution. On the other hand, the CHs are compelled to develop a psyche that the court is the only solution to end structural root causes of suffering. For that, the CHs should have legal awareness and dispose of favourably the pending cases, alongside engaging in dialogue till the outcome and sharing productive relationships with the neighbours. The author alarms whether the CHs' protectionism due to consistent insecurity and resentment is misused in a radical direction by any political or insurgent organisation in the region. The way the issue is compacted in an elastic ballon with increasing pressure with time makes it further complicated from a simple one, therefore, the author fears if the 'society' of the community blasts/collapses at all at risk within the reasons. The author carefully alarms about a precarity, vulnerability, and extinction ahead due to extreme powerlessness embedded in the State's unsettlement policies, necropolitical conspiracy, succumbing social mobility, distrust, internal differences, disorder, and internal fragmentation and fragility.

It is undoubtedly lacking a robust political will, which also shows that there is so much political and strategic interest invested already in the people and government of AP that the CH's interest fulfilment by any chance through the Centre's second direct intervention (once again after the 1960s) may contrabcept the details and result. Strategically speaking, the ECI's role seems critical to balance the counter-interest game-play soon. However, it would be precedented to see, till then, the voting behaviour of the CH voters, their shared enrolment and the remaining impact; yet unforgettable, the State as a powerhouse has so much to do undo. To sum up, the State at its darkest is pushing the nation from a 'confused category' to a 'virtual category' beyond what Anderson (1983/1991) calls an "imagined community". As such, it reflects that anything is possible and simultaneously impossible, impasse and deadlock everywhere. Ghosal (2018) has rightly observed that the marginality of CHs is induced by abject poverty and a confusing identity of statelessness despite permanent rehabilitation.

Therefore, a mixed adventurous feeling from these inputs suggests that the CHs challenge the idea of 'Arunachalee' and an indomitable urge for a 'permanent address' in this universe. In fact, the observations and analysis of facts indicate that the CH urges for a 'location' for fixing their resentment within without bothering the existing shield (the ILP system). Since they are also indigenous by roots and practice, their involvement would further expand the horizons of the dynamic indigeneity of the shield. It is, thus, too helpless with no conflict of interest in line with other authors of concern to share sympathy and solidarity with the rest, seeing them into this big political game of stalemated trap; however, the author agrees that hope is fundamental to a shared humanity.

Endnotes

¹ I am referring the Chakmas and Hajongs of Arunachal Pradesh as a tribe inasmuch as an anthropological category, not political. Conversely, they are indigenous people by social location irrespective of geo-location.

² State with capital ‘S’ refers to State of Arunachal Pradesh indirectly the Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

³ The conceptual intervention of Supergovernment refer to the Government of Arunachal Pradesh having been working influentially beyond the constitutional framework in tandem with several non-state actors. Often, such actors working with state apparatus guide the government with intense pressure, and intimidation of potentially creating law and order problems if their demands are not pursued accordingly. Thus, it becomes a government of the elite group, for the elite group, and by the elite group.

⁴ Amnesty International, No.UA 354/94 INDIA (1994, September 26). Fear for Safety: Chakmas and Hajongs in Arunachal Pradesh. URGENT ACTION — a letter to Central Government, i.e. Prime Minister, Narasimha Rao, and to Arunachal Pradesh Government, the Chief Minister, Gegong Apang; People’s Union for Democratic Rights (1994), *Persecution of Chakmas and Hajongs in Arunachal Pradesh* — a letter to Chief Minister of Arunachal Pradesh by Harish Dhawan, Secretary of PUDR Human Rights Organisation, Delhi.

⁵ I see the CHs as a Citizenship Interns as there is complete absence of clarity over their political status from the side of Central legislation as well as from the local population. It refers to a state of life in-between refugee and citizens; stateless yet in a state; neither fully citizen nor refugee; or partially both at a time, however, towards being and becoming citizen. Internship signals a transitional phase of citizenship test for political reasons which the CHs are undergoing through experiences before entering into the state system or full and equal political community.

⁶ Jhum cultivation or shifting cultivation was highly practised by them, although some of them knew wetland agriculture, the former has been observed more as it suited much of their traditional and ethnic practices while exploring new and open areas of land, jungles, environment and own people.

⁷ The legitimacy of ‘Village Authority’ through ‘Village Committe’ today known as Local Panchayati Raj Institution was withdrawn by the State (Deputy Commissioner, Order No. GA-3/GB/DYN/88/16045-67 (1994, October 11). Changlang, Govt. of Arunachal Pradesh).

⁸ Chakmas do maintain surnames like Roy, Dewan, Talukdar, Karbari, Khisa etc since the colonial period when the respective ancestors believed to have received these titles with certain roles from the Chakma Kingdom. Interestingly, many who had this advantage at a time had undergone through rigorous cultural transformation; for instance, a Chakma women as a wife of a Chakma service holder (having surname of Talukdar) had to have *Sarii* or other attires in some non-residential places, for securing the job only, which in a long term I observed impacted differentially the culturality of their choices, phonetic in Chakma languages, sociality of personal deliberation, and psychologically the pride in being true self of identity in each dimension.

⁹ *Arunachalee* is a term picked up from the field specifying the significance of differential identity of indigenouse people living inside the Inner Line Permit of Arunachal Pradesh. It is originated from Hindi language valuing the feature of origin as well as belonging from Arunachal Pradesh.

¹⁰ People’s Rights Organisation (1993, August 26). *Suspended Between the Promise of*

Citizenship and the Threat of Deportation: Endless Persecution of the stateless Chakmas and Hajongs of Arunachal Pradesh. Urgent Action Appeal to Prime Minister, Narasimha Rao and Minister of Home Affairs, S.B. Chavan.

¹¹ In a shared history, Vijoypur was the only village ablaze and forcible evicted along with arson was done trice in 1989, 1994, 1995, and yet the survivors are still maintaining their livelihood after re-making home. Still there were several other villages evicted with no reason (ibid., p. 234). Till date, the villagers experience such post-incidents traumatic effects.

¹² N.n. (1995, January 15). Chakmas are not to be evicted: NHRC. *The Statesman*. Delhi.

¹³ Khudiram Chakma v. Union Territory of Arunachal Pradesh, 1992 SCC OnLine Gau 17

¹⁴ As noted by the Supreme Court of India, see point 22 of the order: State of Arunachal Pradesh v. Khudiram Chakma, 1994 Supp (1) SCC 615

¹⁵ State of AP took SLP (C) 12429 OF 1992, and Khudiram Chakma has filed SLP (C) No. 13767 of 1992. Thereafter, State of AP Vs Khudiram Chakma, was filed, Civil Appeal No. 2182 of 1993, and Khudiram Chakma Vs State of AP, SLP, Civil Appeal No. 2181 of 1993 in the Apex Court. Both Civil Appeal Nos. 2182 and 2181 of 1993, decided on April 27, 1993.

¹⁶ NEFA was administered by the Governor of Assam, however, not a territory of Assam. It has had own distinctive entity.

¹⁷ Ordinary residents refers to person who stayed during specified period without any serious break (ibid. P. 616).

¹⁸ In Re: Section 6A of the Citizenship Act 1955, 2024 SCC OnLine SC 2880

¹⁹ State of Arunachal Pradesh v. Khudiram Chakma, 1994 Supp (1) SCC 615

²⁰ APITRO Vs. Union of India, WP (C) No. 593 of 1997, order dated November 17, 1997 (SC).; John Moyong V. Union of India, WP (C) No. 13 of 1998, order dated December 9, 2002 (SC)

²¹ People's Union for Civil Liberties Vs Election Commission of India, 2000, WP No. 886 of 2000, decided on September 28, 2000.

²² Chief Electoral Officer, 2019. Itanagar, Arunachal Pradesh.

²³ The author was told by more than 200 rejected CHs applicants across constituencies, between different period of time in 2018 and 2024. In fact, found discrimination where among siblings with similar documents one gets enrolled and the other become rejected.

²⁴ AAPSU and Ors. The Election Commission of India and Ors. (2010), PIL. No. 52 of 2010. The Gauhati High Court.

²⁵ (AAPSU Vs The Election Commission of India & Ors, Petition for Special Leave Petition (Civil) CC. No. 21861 of 2015 and S.L.P (C)...CC No. 17762/2016).

²⁶ Similarly, against the ECI's actions, there are other cases, like W.P. (C) No. 1299/2004; W.P. (C) No. 1692/2004; and W.P. (C) 1551/2004, pending in the Gauhati High Court, filed by Mukut Methi (Former Chief Minister of AP), Kiren Rijju (current Central Minister), and others, respectively.

²⁷ Committee for Citizenship Rights of the Chakmas of Arunachal Pradesh v. State of Arunachal Pradesh, (2016) 15 SCC 540

²⁸ The Supergovernment in the racial dossier label bracketedly the CHs as 'illegal' refugees/foreigners/Bangladeshi/guest because of the process and time when the

CHs were resettled within their indigenous boundaries with some entitled rights by GoI. There was no elected body, political representation and a Statehood as a whole that so far could rightfully give consent or dissent.

²⁹ In the late 1990s, 4,637 applications submitted through proper channels reached MHA once from the local administration, the State Government, however, due to unfulfilment of certain rules, these were returned back to the host State to check again then forward after taking action on it.

³⁰ Member Secretary, Arunachal Pradesh State Legal Services Authority submitted its report to the Supreme Court, dated April 2, 2018, vide No. APSLSA-02/2018.

³¹ Sonaram Chakma and Ors. Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh and Ors. WA Nos. 28(AP) of 2008, 04(AP) of 2009 & 36(AP) of 2010. Decided on Feb 16, 2012.

³² *Supreme Court Review Petition (C)*, No. 3432 of 2015.

³³ *Mirina Chakma Vs. Arunachal Pradesh Public Service Commission & Ors*, W.P(C) No. 766 (A.P)/2017. The Gauhati High Court.

³⁴ *Amal Kumar Chakma and 8 Ors. Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh and 5 Ors* (2022, May 10), PIL 20/2017, The Gauhati High Court.

³⁵ Although there are definitional differences between the refugee and migrants. The author has mixed both because of two reasons: in the official paper of identity certification, they were referred to as refugee migrants, secondly, for the convenience of analysis. In 1960s, there were hundreds of thousands of people from East Pakistan took refuge in India and several thousands were returned later (Weiner, 1993). Following the specific situations as mentioned overleaf, some 14,888 Chakma and Hajong people took refuge in India and later shifted/migrated to the present locations by the Central Government. They were rehabilitated and therefore, never returned. These population is referred to as 'Original' Refugee Migrants.

³⁶ The CHs basic human rights, like Right to life and Personal Liberty were secured vide this judgement: *National Human Rights Commission Vs State of Arunachal Pradesh and Another*, (1996) 1 SCC 742. Supreme Court. 1996 AIR 1234, 1996 SCC (1) 742. Supreme Court of India; The CH got voting rights through this judgement: *Peoples Union of Civil Liberties V. Election commission of India & Ors.*, (2000) WP (C) 490 of 2002, Writ Petition (civil) 509 of 2002 Writ Petition (civil) 515 of 2002. Delhi High Court; Inner Line Permit for the CH not applicable vide these judgments: *Sonaram Chakma and Others V. State of Arunachal Pradesh and Others*, (2012) Court. WA Nos. 28(AP) of 208, 04(AP) of 2009, 36(AP) of 2010. Gauhati High Court. And AAPSU and Ors. The Election Commission of India and Ors. (2010), PIL. No. 52 of 2010. The Gauhati High Court; and

Conferment of Citizenship to the CH vide judgement: *Committee for C.R. Of C.A.P. & Ors Vs. State of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors.* (2015, September 17). AIR 2015 SUPREME COURT 3750, 2016 (15) SCC 540, 2015 AIR SCW 6018, 2016 (1) AJR 534, (2015) 4 SCT 464, (2015) 9 SCALE 787, (2015) 5 INDLD 1, (2015) 155 ALLINDCAS 236 (SC), (2015) 4 KCCR 564.

³⁷ Action Taken Report on 105th Report of the Committee on Petitions of Rajya Sabha, No. RS.2(6)/95-Com.II. (1998, November 02). *letter to Sabimal Bikash Chakma by Deputy Secretary*, Rajya Sabha Secretariat, Parliament of India. See also. Rajya Sabha Secretariat (1997, August). *Rajya Sabha Committee on Petition Hundred and Fifth*

Report. Committee for Citizenship Rights of the Chakmas of Arunachal Pradesh. New Delhi.

³⁸ Descendents refers to those CHs who were born in Arunachal Pradesh from the Original Refugee Migrants. They have a different issue not only based on generational demands on economic prospects, but highly on fixing their legal identity. They are by birth citizenship as specified by the Courts, however, on paper, they enjoy no benefits of citizenship so far as the government schemes/services are concerned.

³⁹ Telephonic Interview with G. Talukdar, a Chakma community right activist from Diyun, AP, on September 3, 2024.

⁴⁰ CRDO demands birth certificate, PRC and ST, including rights of employment, health, ration card, PDS, Panchayati Raj Institution, economic rights and benefits of State and Central schemes; CRDO. (2018, April 18). Mission, *Chakma Rights and Development Organisation*. Arunachal Pradesh. <https://crdo.chakma.in/vision-mission-core-values/> accessed on October 31, 2024.

⁴¹ *Mirina Chakma Vs Arunachal Pradesh Public Service Commission & Ors*, (2017) W.P(C) No. 766 (A.P)/2017. Gauhati High Court.

⁴² Against the September 17, 2015 judgement by the Apex Court, a ‘Review Petition’ signed by the State government and AAPSU challenging the judgement was lodged but instantly dismissed by the Court (SC Review Petition, No. 3432 of 2015).

⁴³ n.n. (2019, July 2). AAPSU discusses SLP on citizenship to refugees. *The Arunachal Times*. <https://arunachaltimes.in/index.php/2019/07/02/aapsu-discusses-slp-on-citizenship-to-refugees/>

⁴⁴ AAPSU letter of Representation to Chief Minister (CM) with written ultimatum words to the government against non-compliance to cancellation of RPC, see, AAPSU (2022, July, 18), *Charter of Demands* to CM, No. AAPSU/CH/RPC/-01-18/22.

Government actioned on it cancelled RPC and rolled TSC: See notification– Joint Secretary (2022, July 30), Notification, No. Pol-12/4/2022, in response to AAPSU Representation, dated. 2022, July 18. Political Department, Govt. of Arunachal Pradesh. See Executive Order—Under Secretary (Political). (2022, July 31). Exec Order No. POL/CH-2/2022-23. Political Department. Govt. of Arunachal Pradesh.

⁴⁵ Nagarwal, Narender. “The Citizenship Amendment Act 2019: An Insight through Constitutional and Secularism Perspective.” *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, (2021). Accessed October 13, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219096211058883>.

⁴⁶ D. Ananda, “The intersection of Indian citizenship amendment act 2019 and religious persecution,” *Discover Global Society* 2, No.76 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44282-024-00108-x>

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